

Application of Electric Potential Method to Smart Composite Structures for Detecting Delamination

Akira TODOROKI, Hideo KOBAYASHI

Department of Mechano-aerospace Engineering,

Tokyo Institute of Technology, 2-12-1, Ohokayama, Meguro-ku, Tokyo 152, Japan
and

Katsuya MATSUURA

Graduate student of Tokyo Institute of Technology

ABSTRACT

CF/Epoxy composites have been applied to many kinds of aircraft structures. The composite laminated plate compression properties, however, are easily decreased by delaminations. Thus an approach for detecting the delaminations, therefore, is intensely desired now. In this study, therefore, an electric potential method was discussed for a real time non-destructive evaluation method of delaminations because this method has several advantages comparing with the embedded optical fiber. In order to obtain the basic properties of the CF/Epoxy composites, mode I and II delamination tests were carried out and the relations between the electric resistance change and the delamination crack length were measured. As a result, the electric resistance bridge circuit approach was proved to be excellent for detecting the delaminations from the inside of the aircraft structures.

INTRODUCTION

Since composite structures of CFRP have superior mechanical properties, the material has been applied to aircraft structures even to primary structures such as main wings. The material, however, has very low delamination resistance. Thus the structures will easily be delaminated by tool dollops or low velocity impacts and consequently the compression properties become awfully low. This causes a bottle neck of designing and the superior properties of the CFRP are underutilized now.

Recently, the smart structures that can detect and repair defects such as cracks or delaminations by embedding sensors or actuators are widely noticed. Therefore, the smart CFRP structure that can detect the delamination in service and inspection by itself has been desired to be developed now. To this end, recently, the smart structures that can detect matrix cracking and delaminations by embedding optical fiber sensors have been developed and been investigated[1]-[3]. However, this method has some problems as follows.

- (1) The embedded optical fiber sensors cannot be applied to already-produced aircraft structures.
- (2) The optical fiber embedding sometimes causes strength decrease.

- (3) It is almost impossible to repair the embedded optical fiber sensors in the case of some accidents of the optical fiber sensors.
- (4) The functional life by the interface debonding between the optical fibers and matrix may cause structural life.

On the base of this background, availability of an electric potential method was investigated in this study because this method is available by attaching electrodes on the surface of the CFRP structures without any special manufacturing. This electric potential system can be applied to the structures in service without strength decrease and the sensor repair is relatively easy. As generally known, there are electric-conduction carbon fibers and electric-insulation resin matrix in the CFRP. The electric potential method is just an approach that uses reinforcement carbon fibers as sensors. However, the electric resistance property of the CFRP is not well known. Thus the experimental basic investigations are needed. For this purpose, delamination crack length was measured by the electric potential method with unidirectionally stacked laminate specimens.

SPECIMENS AND EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

Material used is T300/epoxy (Torey P3051-25; cured condition = $130^{\circ} \text{C} \times 0.4 \text{MPa} \times 1.5 \text{H}$) and the stacking sequence is $[0]_8 \text{T}$. Artificial defects were induced by inserting Teflon film of 30 mm length between the middle thickness plies. Specimens of the length $L=200 \text{mm}$, width $B=20 \text{mm}$ and thickness $2H=2 \text{mm}$ were manufactured from the CFRP plates. Mode I delamination experiments and mode II delamination experiments were conducted by using the specimens. These specimens and jigs are shown in Figure 1 and Figure 2 respectively.

Figure 1 Mode I specimen and electrodes

Figure 2 Mode II specimen and electrodes

Block type jigs made from Aluminum alloy were used in the mode I double-cantilever tests[4]. In order to keep electric insurance, GFRP laminates were inserted between jigs and specimens and attached to both jigs and specimens with epoxy type adhesive agent in this study. The experiments were conducted by using a hydro-static-servo-testing-machine under the displacement controlled condition with loading ratio 1.5mm/min. Delamination crack length was measured with reading microscopes from the specimen side during the test under the load holding condition.

End notched flexure (ENF) tests were conducted in the mode II test with three points bending jigs. Since the delamination crack front has a large zigzag shape in the mode II test[5], the delamination crack length was measured by using a compliance method. The compliance method used relations between load and loading point displacement in this study. This method is proved to be effective by using a scanning acoustic microscope by a part of authors[6].

Electrodes were examined by using carbon tape, aluminum tape, silver paste, carbon paste, aluminum plate, and copper plate. After this trial-and-error, the best electrode is decided as follows.

- (1) After polishing a specimen surface by relatively rough sand paper, the surface was washed by acetone.
- (2) Silver paste is painted on the washed surface.
- (3) A pair of strain gauge terminals is attached by adhesive agent. An electrode is made by this pair of terminals. The distance between these terminals is about 10mm and aligned with a perpendicular line to the crack growth direction.
- (4) A lead wire is soldered to the each terminal.
- (5) Electric conductivity is arranged by painting silver paint between the lead wire and the specimen.
- (6) The electrode is covered with aluminum tape in order to fix the electrode.

Two kinds of electron potential methods were examined in this study. One is the same as conventional electron potential method in which large direct electric current is used and electric voltage change is measured to obtain the specimen electric resistance change. This is called as a conventional method in this study. The other is an electron resistance bridge circuit method and this is called a bridge method in this study. The sectional structure of an electrode is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 Structure of electrode

Figure 4 Electric resistance bridge method

Two types of electrode positions of specimens were examined. Type A-A' has two electrodes in opposite side of the delamination crack as shown in Figure 1. Type A-B has the electrodes in the same side of the delamination crack on the assumption that the electrodes can be attached inside the aircraft structures.

Since electric resistance of the specimens is very small (about $4\ \Omega$ between A-A' and $2\ \Omega$ between A-B), it is difficult to make the electric resistance bridge stable. Thus the high precise resistance of $120\ \Omega$ was connected in series to make it stable. This schema is shown in Figure 4. The variable resistance of $10\ \Omega$ is used in this figure. The electron resistance bridge was connected to a direct current strain amplifier on the market. This equipment uses low electric current and amplifies the voltage change between the bridge with high precision.

EXPERIMENTS AND DISCUSSIONS

MODE I TESTS

The obtained relation between increment of delamination crack Δa and resistance change ratio $\Delta R/R_0$ by using the conventional method is shown in Figure 5. In this figure, the A_0 shows the change between electrodes. Though the change was measured by using several electric current input levels, only the typical data by using the current of $0.7\ \text{A}$ is shown in Figure 5. The perpendicular axis is resistance change ΔR normalized by an initial resistance R_0 . The horizontal axis is delamination crack length increment Δa normalized by a specimen length L . The resistance change was calculated by using Ohm's law with the measured electric voltage data. Linear increase of the resistance with the delamination crack increment can be observed in all electrodes as shown in the figure by using the conventional method. On the basis of this result, it was proved that the delamination crack can also be detected by using the conventional method.

In the conventional method, resistance change with delamination crack growth could be measured as shown in Figure 5. However, this method needed waiting time after delamination crack growth before measuring because the output was not stable during about 10 minutes. In order to investigate this reason, specimen temperature change was measured with various input currents with thermo-couple. As a result, temperature stabilizing time was about 10 minutes and the stabilized temperature rose to $50^\circ\ \text{C}$.

As described above, the conventional method has some problems for sensors of smart structures. The problems are as follows.

- (1) Waiting time for stabilization is too long.
- (2) Large current is needed to high precision detecting.
- (3) Electric power consumption is too large.
- (4) Temperature-rise of a specimen cannot be neglected.

Figure 5 Experimental results by the conventional method (Mode I, A-A')

The new bridge method proposed in this study uses low electric current and has high precision. The bridge method, therefore, as shown in Figure 4, gives the answer to the problems that the specimen temperature is elevated by the high electric current. Experimental results obtained by using the bridge method of type A-A' is shown in Figure 6. The horizontal axis is delamination crack increment normalized by the specimen length and the perpendicular axis is the specimen electric resistance change. Circle symbols and triangle symbols show the results of different specimen respectively. This figure shows that the electric resistance change is almost linear with the crack growth. Moreover, there is no difference between results of the two specimens. The method, therefore, is proved to be effective for detecting delamination cracks.

Figure 6 Experimental results by the bridge method (Mode I, A-A' Method)

This method does not need longer waiting time for measurements than 1 minute and even if it measured without waiting time, the difference is very small (the open triangle symbols show the results without waiting and solid symbols shows results after 1 minute waiting). From this point,

it is understood that stabilization-waiting-time is not needed in the bridge method. The bridge voltage was 4 V and the maximum electric current was 30 mA. This small current causes no elevated temperature in specimens. Therefore, the bridge method is proved to be appropriate for the sensors of smart structures.

Experimental results obtained by using the bridge method of the type A-B is shown in Figure 7. The type A-B is a simplified model that the all sensor electrodes are assumed to be attached inside of the aircraft. In this case, the resistance change ratio is about 1/5. This is very small change comparing the type A-A'. This resistance increase from the initial value (2Ω) is supposed to be caused by decreasing the electric conductive cross section with the delamination crack growth. The triangle symbols and circle symbols show the results of different specimens and the difference is relatively large. Moreover, the non-linear relation was obtained with the delamination crack growth.

Figure 7 Experimental results of resistance change (Mode I, A-B Method)

The non-linear relation is supposed to be caused by the relatively low reliability of the electrodes. In the case of the type A-A', as the resistance increase is relatively large, the electric resistance variation by the specimen deformation can be neglected. On the contrary, in the case of the type A-B, the electric resistance change is small and the electric resistance change by specimen deformation is supposed to be relatively large. Thus the more reliable electrode is needed in the actual smart structures. Since the resistance change is able to be measured, the type A-B method is proved to be appropriate for the sensors of smart structures.

MODE II TESTS

Since the effectiveness of the bridge method for the smart structural sensors has been proved by the mode I experiments, the bridge method was examined in mode II tests. In the mode II tests, the delamination crack propagates by shearing stress. Thus the delamination crack surfaces keep contact with each other during the mode II test loading. The loading condition is very different from that of mode I and the loading condition of the actual delamination crack is supposed to be similar to the mode II test because the actual delamination by drop weights is caused by shearing and tearing.

The experimental results obtained of type A-A' are shown in Figure 8. The perpendicular axis and horizontal axis are the same as that of mode I. From this figure, it is revealed that the electric resistance increases almost linearly with the delamination crack growth even in the mode II test in which the delamination crack surfaces keep contact with each other. Moreover, the increase ratio is similar to that of mode I. The triangle symbols and circle symbols show the results of different specimens respectively. These results almost agree with each other. The solid symbols are the result with stabilizing waiting and the open symbols are the results without it. There is no difference between them. As a result, the bridge method is proved to be effective even in the mode II case.

Figure 8 Experimental results by the bridge method (Mode II, A-A' Method)

Figure 9 Experimental results by the bridge method (Mode I, A-B Method)

The experimental results obtained of the type A-B are shown on Figure 9. This figure shows the linear increase of the electric resistance with the delamination crack growth in the case of the type A-B. The increment ratio, however, is very small and is almost 1/5 of that of mode I shown in Figure 5. In the case of the type A-A', the increment ratio is almost the same as that of mode I. In the case of the type A-B, however, the ratio becomes smaller than that of mode I. This cause is not clear and will be investigated in future. However, it can be conclude that the delamination crack is proved to be detectable even in the case of the type A-B of mode II test. Provided that the delamination crack of mode II propagates unstably under the condition of $a/L < 0.7$, the impact causes relatively large electric resistance change of electrodes and the delamination crack could not be detected. Thus the reliability of the electrodes is very important in the case that there is small resistance change such as the type A-B.

CONCLUSIONS

Delamination tests were conducted with unidirectionally stacked CFRP lamina and the effectiveness of the electric potential method for the sensors of the smart structures was investigated here. Results obtained are as follows.

(1) The conventional constant direct current potential method needs high electric current for high precision and this causes temperature elevation. Moreover the elevated temperature leads to the necessity of the long waiting time for stabilizing. Therefore, this method is not appropriate for the sensor of the smart structures.

(2) The bridge method needs low current and gives high precise measurements. This method is appropriate for the sensor of the smart structures.

(3) By using the bridge method, delamination crack can be detected even in the case that both of the electrodes are attached on the same specimen surface which simulates the electrodes are attached inside the airplane though the output change is relatively small.

(4) Even in the case of the mode II test in which the delamination crack surfaces keep contact with each other, the delamination crack can be detected similar to that of the mode I.

REFERENCES

- (1) Shintarou KITADE, Taketo HUKUDA and Katsuhiko OOSAKA, Influence of Embedded Optical Fibers on Interlaminar Shear Strength of Composite Laminates, Proceeding of 22th FRP symposium, (1992), p.38. (in Japanese)
- (2) B. Hofer, Fibre Optic Damage Detection in Composites Structures, Composites, vol.18, No.4, (1987), p.309.
- (3) S.R. Waite and G.N. Sage, The failure of Optical Fibers Embedded in Composite Materials, Composites, vol.19, No.4, (1988) p.288.
- (4) Kazuro KAGEYAMA, Takayuki KOBAYASHI, Noboru YANAGISAWA, Masaki KIKUCHI and Hiroshi MIYAMOTO, Mode I Interlaminar Fracture Mechanics of Unidirectionally Reinforced Carbon/Nylon Laminates, Trans. of the Japan Soc. of Mech. Eng., vol.53, A, (1987), p.2386. (in Japanese).
- (5) Akira TODOROKI and Hideo KOBAYASHI, Evaluation of Delamination Fracture Toughness of High-Strength CFRP and Micromechanism, Trans. of the Japan Soc. of Mech. Eng., vol.57, No.539, A, (1991), p.1648. (in Japanese).
- (6) Akira TODOROKI, Hideo KOBAYASHI and Jong Gi LEE, Observation of Delamination Crack Initiation of Composites by SAM, Proceeding of the 1992 Annual Meeting of JSME/MMD, No.920-72, (1992), p.373.
- (7) Kazumasa MORIYA and Takashi ENDO, A Study on Flow Detection Method for CFRP Composite Laminates (1st Report) The Measurement of Crack Extension in CFRP Composites by Electrical Potential Method, J. of the Japan Soc. for Aeronautical and Space Science, vol.36, No.410, (1988), p.139. (in Japanese).